

The green & eco-friendly biosynthesized biocompatible metallic silver nanoparticles for anti-bacterial and anti-biofilm efficacy

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Abstract

The existing work was based on a prudent & environmentally affordable outlook for a green biological mode of synthesis of nanoparticles (NPs) in an aqueous solvent system. In order to biologically synthesized NPs, the plant leaves were used. Subsequently, the anti-bacterial assessment of NPs evaluated the bacterial activities of multidrug-resistant clinical isolates. The bacterial growth rate, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), & biofilm formation were explored in *S. aureus* clinical isolates. The results exposed that NPs were more effective with varying anti-bacterial potential against bacterial growth, planktonic cell & biofilm formations. The protein degradation assay shows mechanisms of ROS formation & lipid bilayer visualization suggesting that protein & peptide degradation through intrinsic NPs accumulations. In judgement, our outcome accompanies that the appearance of protein shells on AgNPs can mitigate biofilm formation, especially in clinical isolates at low concentrations. It opens new avenues for silver NPs to attune & strengthen their valuable qualities.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, hospital-acquired infections, biofilm, ROS, size effect

Introduction

The NPs produced by the biological process as compared to chemical reactivity, especially from the plant mode, are eco-friendly with nature & more biocompatible for living animals. Technical & environ issues in the fields of stellar power transformation, enzyme catalysis, therapeutic, & aqua analysis with treatment are used as applications of nanomaterials. "Eco freak" biochemistry & biochemical proceedings are steadily involved in technology, science & industry trade for viable expansions. The NPs have the properties of a more extensive exterior to-bulk ratio relatively than the individual outcome of metal ion delivery as an anti-bacterial effect^[1]. A large exterior to volume proportion is usually followed by escalated manufacture of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and free radical formation. In recent research, the approach suggested that the nanomaterials explored as anti-microbial agents have negligible resistance^[2]. The novelty is nano size for potent work as drug delivery for efficient tool in infectious diseases, reducing toxicity, lowering cost & drug resistance compared to drugs. NPs allow interaction firmly with microbial membranes, impair their interior composition & inactivate microbes^[3]. The metallic NPs are of particular curiosity as a microbicidal factor, as they can be synthesized with huge surface zone & unique crystalline, amorphous surface structures with many fringe & intersections & other inherent active spots^[4]. NPs are effective nano-coups that are advanced & effective in catching biofilm infections & inhibit the bacterial cells & their severity^[5]. Chronic infectious biofilm is an exasperating problem for humanity. The microbial resistance, especially bacterial resistance to drugs available on the market, assures that further developing a new anti-microbial entity will be effective^[6]. The microbes are convoluted as resistance to drugs against bacterial infectious diseases threaten humanity^[7] the current condition of drug-resistant contagious diseases facing severe issues worldwide. Day by day, bacterial resistance increases with the side effects of drugs resulting in a high mortality rate with a high health cost. *S. aureus* is a gram-positive, omnipresent bacterial species^[8]. It contributes an essential character in the case of human beings causing severe circumstances & painful conditions such as subclinical sensitivity to acute inflammation leading to develop pneumonia (respiratory disease), infective endocarditis (IE) & septic infection. Currently, vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) & methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (VRSA) multifunctional antidote impenetrable *S. aureus* has been difficult to cure with shoot-up mortality rates^[9]. The hollow nasal space is the fundamental source for *S. aureus*. The significant population of the USA, the UK, Japan, & other countries is seized with the *S. aureus* pathogen. Nevertheless, the infection & colonialism may cause a risk factor for severity. Previous research explored that it has a sturdy causative link allying *S. aureus* nasal conveyance of human beings & a higher threat of severe nosocomial inflammation. The nasal cavity has mucous fluid as a carrier imparting a direct ground for *S. aureus* to circulate & invade another region of the biofluid and pass on to the vascular system through an epithelial tissue, planktonic extension & upregulated attachment occur severity & lead to adhere the extracellular matrix form which finally forms a biofilm^[10]. Hence predilection modifies from severe inflammation to one that is determined, chronic & repetitive. This continues to receive substantial recognition in recent approaches to exploring nanomaterials that received much focus due to their anti-microbial properties. Nanotechnology is a

modern research technique that inspires has good qualities such as nano-size, a high surface-to-volume area, eco-friendliness, nontoxic molecules, solvents, & non-costlier process for large-scale production. The effect of NPs against infectious diseases' produces as reducing toxicity, lowering cost & drug resistance to compared drugs^[11]. NPs are particulars with unique magnetic characteristics & better biocompatibility. Therefore, the intention of the research work intended to examine the result of AgNPs on the biofilm production of *S. aureus* & their clinical isolates, which were covid & post covid patients. The anti-microbial activities of *S. aureus* on planktonic cell growth inhibition & antibiofilm were performed & using different concentrations of silver NPs against the biofilm of bacteria was assessed successfully^[12].

Methods

Requirements

Chandigarh, India. GMH01 & GMH02 clinical isolates were received from Medical College Nanded. All bacterial culture was grown in nutrient agar slants & kept at 4°C for the experiment.

Instruments: Multiplate reader (Synergy HTX, USA), Incubator & Stirrer etc.

1. Biosynthesis of TPL AgNPs & characterization

The deliquescent extract of plant leaf *Thevetia peruviana* was used for the synthesis & characterization of TPL AgNPs as given in the literature & followed the protocol^[3].

2. Anti-bacterial activities of TPL AgNPs

In the agar by well diffusion method, bacterial activities of the TPL AgNPs were determined in the nutrient medium. Briefly, the bacterial cells were grown in a culture medium of test bacteria. They were used to get standard inoculums by maintaining opacity approximate to the grade 0.5 McFarland suspension at 600 nm. This bacterial cell suspension was spread consistently over a NA plate. The sterilized cork borer was made of 6 mm circumference in each agar plate. By agar dilution method, we study the bactericidal activity of TPL AgNPs on *S. aureus* ATCC00435 strain I.e. GMH01 & GMH02. Bacterial nutrient agar was supplemented with various concentrations of TPL AgNPs (10 to 100 g/mL). Each plate was inoculated with 10⁷ CFU/mL of GMH01, GMH02 strain of *S. aureus* by spread plating. After that, plates inoculated with bacterial *S. aureus* ATCC00435, GMH01 & GMH02 but without TPL AgNPs have used as negative control & 2.5 mg/mL of chloramphenicol a standard antibiotic as a positive control. 50 µL of TPL AgNPs extract & control was poured into the wells, & 50 µL of positive control was poured into the other wells & were incubated full night at 37°C. Survival colonies of bacteria in the form of the zone of inhibitions (ZOI) were observed in agar plates following 24 hr of incubation at 37 °C. Experiments were repeated thrice^[12].

3. Determination of minimum inhibition concentrations (MIC)

The *S. aureus* clinical isolates GMH01 & GMH02 resulted in clear vulnerability to the treated reactants with the agar diffusion assay & were tested using the MIC & after with the microdilution protocol. Two-fold dilutions were made for the tested compounds (TPL extract, AgNO₃, & TPL AgNPs) at 50 µ/mL. TPL AgNPs were diluted with 99 % DMSO solution. The DMSO showed no effect in the pre-experimental phase on microbial growth. Therefore, serial two-fold dilutions were prepared in DMSO & served as a negative control. The chloramphenicol was used as a positive control. Later on, in each well, 100 µL of sterile nutrient broth was added. In the next step, the plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C. The microtiter plate reader was used to check the bacterial growth & it was measured with the help of absorbance at 959 nm^[13].

4. Quantification of minimal bactericidal concentration (MBC)

Sequential dilution of 100 µg/mL TPL AgNPs in cell suspension was added to the 96 well on the NA plate. MBC was elucidated as the utmost dilution that discloses no microbial colony. MIC/MBC was analysed by strain & their clinical isolates^[3].

5. Bacterial growth kinetic analysis

The growth kinetics analysis was carried out in the appearance & absence of different concentrations of NPs (0 to 100 µg/mL) incubated at 37 °C. The bacterial suspension in a medium without NPs considered control. Briefly, inoculum suspensions of both strain & their clinical isolates of bacteria were made. In brief, about 100 µL of bacterial suspension was adjoined to every 96 well plates. In the next step, the concentrations of NPs were affixed to the specific reaction fusion. The growth & expansion of microbial species were analysed regularly with the help of a microtiter plate reader by measuring absorbance at 600 nm^[14].

6. Colony-forming unit estimation (CFU)

To estimate the CFU, 50 µL of the test solution was obtained from the stationary phase of the microbial growth kinetics experiment & added to PBS sequentially for dilution. After this, 10 µL of the final diluted solution was poured into NA plates & incubated at 37 °C. The colonies were counted & inspect with positive control after 24 hr of incubation was over. This experiment was performed in multiples for authentication^[15].

7. Anti-biofilm analysis

8. Hindrance of biofilm emergence

The action of the TPL AgNPs on biofilm production was analysed through a procedure previously explained [3]. The culture was separated from the bacterial expansion kinetics experimental wells & it was washed thrice with PBS & with 0.1 % crystal violet stain & kept for staining for about 15 min. The excessive stain was removed via washing with PBS, & the plate was soaked in the oven. Once vessel was dried nicely, the stained cells which were adhered dissolved in 30 % of acetic acid, & optical density (OD) was measured at 600 nm. The whole procedure was repeated multiple for confirmation.

The outcome of TPL AgNPs biofilm formation was calculated as follows

$$\text{Inhibition percentage} = \{ \text{OD of the control} - \text{OD of the sample} \} / \text{OD of the control} \times 100$$

9. SEM

Scanning electron microscopic images were captured for analysis of results for both the ATCC00435 & isolated strain of GMH01 & GMH02 of *S. aureus* bacteria (fig 4 A).

Statistical analysis

Results in the above experiments were represented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was used to study statistically significant variables between the microbes (SPSS 14, Chicago, USA) tested & was accustomed to carrying out the data examination.

Results and Discussions

Fig 1: A) Growth Inhibitions of *S. aureus* by agar diffusion assay a) ATCC00435 strains and b) clinical isolates GMH01, c) GMH02 strains treated with TPL AgNPs

The biologically synthesized TPL AgNPs characterized previously were reported [3]. These TPL AgNPs were utilized to conduct anti-bacterial evaluation & the results were obtained, which showed effective inhibition indicated ZOI (Fig. 1. A). The outcomes of the current study explained the anti-bacterial efficiency (Table 1.). The maximum ZOI was observed for the *S. aureus* clinical isolates GMH01 strain (22 ± 0.1 mm), & the minimum ZOI was calculated for *S. aureus* & clinical isolates GMH01 (16 ± 0.50 mm). The obtained results showed a more robust anti-microbial efficacy than formerly described data. The bacterial growth kinetic research, planktonic cell growth assay & biofilm of *S. aureus* & their clinical isolates against TPL AgNPs synthesized from *Thevitia peruviana* leaf extract were performed with different concentrations. Bacteria studies (Fig.1. A) confirmed a considerably high growth inhibition compared to their respective controls. This study confirmed that at lower concentrations, it did not show any good effect (the concentration of $50 \mu\text{g/mL}$) of TPL AgNPs, for both the bacteria & their clinical isolates. The Planktonic cell growth assessment (Fig.1 A) indicated that both the bacterial cells & isolates significantly decreased with the rising concentration of TPL AgNPs, confirming a great anti-microbial potential of TPL AgNPs against bacteria & clinical isolates. The CFU determination was used to evaluate the MIC of TPL AgNPs. The planktonic cell growth inhibitions are also considered MIC, the smallest concentration that inhibited microbial growth was ≥ 50 %. The CFU data showed that the minimum concentrations, such as 25 & $50 \mu\text{g/mL}$, can reduce the cell expansion of gram-positive bacteria & clinical strains easily. The total inhibition of bacterial & clinical strain MBC was $200 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Biofilm synthesis is the most important step of crucial inflammations, promotes resistance & provides almost 80 % of

infectious diseases solely ^[1]. By exploring the fact that the scientist opined, that targeting biofilm is a strategy to achieve control on the microbes ^[17], the anti-biofilm action of the TPL AgNPs were evaluated successfully.

Fig 2: Planktonic cell growth of *S. aureus* ATCC00435 strains and clinical isolates GMH01, GMH02 treated with TPL AgNPs

Observation & result of the present study explored that the production of biofilm was decreased upto 30 - 87 % with the rise in the concentration of the TPL AgNPs compared to control (Fig. 3). The biofilm production was reduced upto 66 - 75 % at their particular MIC (Fig. 3., Table. 1). In addition, the effects of TPL AgNPs on already established biofilms were also determined. The formed biofilms approximately 65 - 78 % were remarkably inhibited at the largest concentration i.e. 100 µg/mL & 50 µg/mL of the TPL AgNPs (Fig. 2). In comparing clinical isolates, about 55 - 57 % of inhibitions were found for their related MIC concentration of biofilm formations. But the smaller concentrations such as 25 µg/mL, did not show enough capability to stop biofilm production. The current research indicated that the MIC of the TPL AgNPs was not only important but also confines the growth of biofilm formation. The scanning & simple microscopy images also revealed the inhibition of bacterial cells compared to the control ones (Fig. 5 A, B, C). The inhibited cells were reduced in number & shrunk compared to the control ones (Fig. 2). The outcomes of the current studied data were so close to those previously reported where TPL AgNPs were a more prominent killer of the gram-negative & gram-positive bacteria ^[3]. The most accepted hypothesis for the action of AgNPs is an attraction between positively charged particles toward negatively charged microbes as membrane permeability of charged ions with NPs disturbs cellular functions & ultimately causes cell death ^[16]. The endocytosis process of the bacterial membrane seems to disturb the cell's metabolism, leading to cell death. In addition, another probable reason for the AgNPs action mechanism is that the gram-negative bacteria are enclosed with a slimy fine lipo-polysaccharides covering which disintegrates more easily as compared to the thick and little tough peptidoglycan covering of the gram-positive bacteria ^[17]. According to the previously published report studies it was found that the CT molecule could adhere to the cell exterior & stops the nutrient supply path between the bacterial cells & their surroundings ^[18]. In the current research, the TPL AgNPs exhibited better anti-microbial & antibiofilm efficiencies were observed.

Table 1: Comparison of MICs of TPL AgNPs against planktonic and bio growth of *S. aureus* ATCC00435 strain, and clinical isolates GMH01, G-H02 strains

<i>S. aureus</i>	MIC (µg/mL)		MFC (µg/mL)
	Planktonic Cell	Biofilm Development	
ATCC00435	50	100	200
GMH 01	25	50	200
GMH 02	25	50	200

Fig 3: Biofilm growth formation of *S. aureus* ATCC00435 strain and clinical isolates GMH01, GMH02 strains treated with TPL AgNPs

Fig 4: A) SEM images a) & b), B) Simple microscopy c) & d), C) Biofilm growth of *S. aureus* ATCC00435 strain treated with TPL AgNPs

Moreover, this experiment studied probable and related anti-microbial sensitivity issues for NPs to those observed in the literature survey ^[19]. The anti-bacterial mechanism of NPs was able to produce ROS were reported in our original study. The bacterial cell wall composition plays an important role in the action of NPs as they are gram-positive and gram-negative due to membrane content ^[20]. In the earlier published records, the semiconductor nature of AgNPs with a lesser band gap for photocatalytic activity has been observed. Generally, the presence of the different lone pair valencies in the conduction band of AgNPs is the cause of redox (oxidation-reduction) reactions, producing more electron lone pairs that create the free radicals via cycling of reactions ^[21]. The holes present on the outer surface of NPs were reacted with water to produce a hydroxyl [OH⁻] free radicals, while the lone pair electrons in the conduction band react with dissolved O₂ moieties to form a superoxide anions which perform the role of anti-microbial activity. Moreover, the various experiments showed that the anti-microbial property of such NPs can be upgraded by attuning the band gap energy ^[22]. The other mechanism to tune the band gap energy is to coat the NPs surfaces. Therefore, it causes a rise in the action of electrons from the valence band to the conduction band of the NPs, resulting in the enhancement of ROS synthesis. A similar case might be with the TPL AgNPs. though, still, there is a need for detailed study and investigations in-depth were required to reveal the exact mechanism of bactericidal properties ^[23]. To the best of our knowledge, This research on TPL AgNPs synthesized using *Thevetia peruviana* plant leaf extract was the first we did for different bactericidal & biofilm inhibiting reactions on *S. aureus* ^[24] & along with their clinical isolates.

Conclusions

In this study, the naturally synthesized TPL AgNPs were used to efficiently targets bacterial pathogens with their clinical isolates. The NPs size was around 20 nm in range, effectively killing the bacterial cells. The NPs efficiently integrate into the bacterial cell wall & the $\geq 50 \mu\text{g/mL}$ of concentration was effective to cause higher mortality and adequately decrease the biofilm viable cell count & making the nano-material for a biofilm-related cure. The current investigations showed the usefulness of TPL AgNPs products in the anti-bacterial & anti-biofilm study of *S. aureus* with their clinical isolates. The anti-parasitic and insecticidal activity of the TPL AgNPs is an upcoming target of the study.

Conflict of interest statement

All the author declares there is no conflict of interest to mention.

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References

1. Ibrahim Khan, Khalid Saeed, Idrees Khan. Nanoparticles: Properties, applications and toxicities, Arabian Journal of Chemistry,2019;12(7):908-931. ISSN 1878-5352, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2017.05.011>.
2. Wang L, Hu C, Shao L. The anti-microbial activity of nanoparticles: present situation & prospects for the future. International journal of nanomedicine,2017;12:1227-1249. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S121956>
3. Das YK, Ghar SB, Mulani RM, Karuppayil SM. CSH, ADHESION & ANTI-BIOFILM STUDIES OF TPL AGNPS USING CENTRAL VENOUS CATHETER MODEL, IRJMETS,2021;3(5):837-849 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.64096712021/5/5>
4. Sirelkhatim A, Mahmud S, Seeni A, Kaus N, Ann LC, Bakhori S *et al.* Review on Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles: Anti-bacterial Activity and Toxicity Mechanism. Nano-micro letters,2015;7(3):219-242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-015-0040-x>
5. Dos Santos Ramos MA, Da Silva PB, Spósito L, De Toledo LG, Bonifácio BV, Rodero CF *et al.* Nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems for control of microbial biofilms: a review. International journal of nanomedicine,2018;13:1179-1213.
6. Das YK, Ghar SB, Mulani RM, Karuppayil SM. BiTCoN: A Bimodal Therapy Against Candida Albicans. IJSRED,2021;4(3):27-41. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6409494>
7. Dadgostar P. Anti-microbial Resistance: Implications and Costs. Infection and drug resistance,2019;12:3903-3910. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S234610>
8. Clark SB, Hicks MA. Staphylococcal Pneumonia. [Updated 2022 Jan 31]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): Stat Pearls Publishing, 2022. Jan. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559152/>
9. Sakr A, Brégeon F, Mège JL, Rolain JM, Blin O. *Staphylococcus aureus* Nasal Colonization: An Update on Mechanisms, Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Subsequent Infections. Frontiers in microbiology,2018;9:2419. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.02419>
10. Thiruvengadam M, Rajakumar G, Chung IM. Nanotechnology: current uses and future applications in the food industry,2018;3:8(1):74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-018-1104-7>
11. Berini Francesca, Orlandi Viviana Teresa, Gamberoni Federica, Martegani Eleonora, Armenia Ilaria, Gornati Rosalba *et al.* Anti-microbial Activity of Nanoconjugated Glycopeptide Antibiotics and Their Effect on *Staphylococcus aureus* Biofilm Frontiers in Microbiology,2021;12:10. 3389/fmicb.2021.657431

12. Balouiri M, Sadiki M, Ibsouda SK. Methods for *in vitro* evaluating anti-microbial activity: A review. *Journal of pharmaceutical analysis*,2016;6(2):71-79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpha.2015.11.005>
13. Adhikari R, Pant ND, Neupane S, Neupane M, Bhattarai R, Bhatta S *et al.* Detection of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of Vancomycin for *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolated from Pus/Wound Swab Samples of the Patients Attending a Tertiary Care Hospital in Kathmandu, Nepal. *The Canadian journal of infectious diseases and medical microbiology = Journal canadien des maladies infectieuses et de la microbiologie medicale*,2017, 2191532. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/219153>
14. Gouyau J, Duval RE, Boudier A, Lamouroux E. Investigation of Nanoparticle Metallic Core Anti-bacterial Activity: Gold and Silver Nanoparticles against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *International journal of molecular sciences*,2021;22(4):1905. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22041905>
15. Davis KE, Joseph SJ, Janssen PH. Effects of growth medium, inoculum size, and incubation time on culturability and isolation of soil bacteria. *Applied and environmental microbiology*,2005;71(2):826-834. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.2.826-834.2005>
16. Donlan RM, Costerton JW. Biofilms: survival mechanisms of clinically relevant microorganisms. *Clinical microbiology reviews*,2002;15(2):167-193. <https://doi.org/10.1128/CMR.15.2.167-193.2002>
17. Dakal TC, Kumar A, Majumdar RS, Yadav V. Mechanistic Basis of Anti-microbial Actions of Silver Nanoparticles. *Frontiers in microbiology*,2016;7:1831. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.01831>
18. Silhavy TJ, Kahne D, Walker S. The bacterial cell envelope. *Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in biology*,2010;2(5):a000414. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a000414>
19. Varki A. Biological roles of glycans. *Glycobiology*,2017;2:7(1):3-49. <https://doi.org/10.1093/glycob/cww086>
20. Franci G, Falanga A, Galdiero S, Palomba L, Rai M, Morelli G *et al.* Silver nanoparticles as potential anti-bacterial agents. *Molecules* (Basel, Switzerland),2015;20(5):8856-8874. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules20058856>
21. Zonaro E, Lampis S, Turner RJ, Qazi SJ, Vallini G. Biogenic selenium and tellurium nanoparticles synthesized by environmental microbial isolates efficaciously inhibit bacterial planktonic cultures and biofilms. *Frontiers in microbiology*,2015;6:584. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2015.00584>
22. Liao C, Li Y, Tjong SC. Visible-Light Active Titanium Dioxide Nanomaterials with Bactericidal Properties. *Nanomaterials* (Basel, Switzerland),2020;10(1):124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10010124>
23. Byrne JA, Dunlop PS, Hamilton JW, Fernández-Ibáñez P, Polo-López I, Sharma PK *et al.* A review of heterogeneous photocatalysis for water and surface disinfection. *Molecules* (Basel, Switzerland),2015;20(4):5574-5615. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules20045574>
24. Lee SH, Jun BH. Silver Nanoparticles: Synthesis and Application for Nanomedicine. *International journal of molecular sciences*,2019;20(4):865. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20040865>